

INTENSIVE METHODS OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATION

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Annotation: In this article, the intensive methods of English in preschool education, the use of innovative methods in teaching English in preschool education, explaining the methodology of language materials to language learners, the law that has caused positive updates in preschool education are fully explained. .

Key words: methodology, pedagogical principles, positive updates, innovative methods.

Introduction:

It is known that the English language is rapidly improving nowadays. Also, this acceleration has not left our country. Of course, this is a sign of great development for our country and for people. That's why it is advisable to implement it in a unique experiment, in a tested form, in English language teaching.

The idea of developing threshold levels as specific goals of foreign language acquisition was formed. Originally intended mainly for older students, it has been adapted with great success to the educational goals and content of schools and other educational institutions.

Literature analysis and methodology:

Preschool education can teach children language not as an obligation, but on the contrary, using interesting games and innovative methods, which can serve as a foundation for their future knowledge. Therefore, as the educational system also sets itself the task of educating a free-thinking, well-rounded, mature person, in the future, we, future teachers, will better develop ways to effectively use innovative technologies. we can contribute.

It is known that it is very convenient to start learning a foreign language in preschool education. Children of this age are distinguished by their sensitivity to language phenomena, they are interested in understanding their speech experiences, the "secrets" of language. They easily and firmly remember a small amount of language material and multiply it well. With age, these favorable factors lose their power.

There is another reason why an early age is preferable for learning a foreign language. The younger the child, the smaller the vocabulary in the local language, but at the same time his needs for speech are less: a small child has less areas of communication than an adult, he still has to solve complex communication problems it's not. This means that when he learns a foreign language, he does not notice such a big difference between the opportunities in his mother tongue and foreign languages, and his sense of success is brighter than that of older children.

Results:

Teaching children is a very difficult issue that requires a completely different methodological approach than schoolchildren and adults. If an adult speaks a foreign language, it does not mean that he can teach others. When faced with methodologically inefficient lessons, children can long-term hate the foreign language and lose confidence in their abilities. This means that only experienced specialists should work with preschool children. It consists of:

- formation of children's basic communication skills in a foreign language;
- the ability to use a foreign language to achieve one's goals, to express one's thoughts and feelings in life communication;
- to create a positive attitude to further study of foreign languages;
- arouse interest in the life and culture of other countries.

Therefore, the methodical requirements for the organization of the lesson should be strict. For this, it is necessary that it be interesting and suitable for children's ability (language learning). The organization of learning language material should be built on the basis of conscious, independence, which corresponds to the young characteristics of students.

Discussion:

Traditional and interactive teaching methods are used in the process of teaching foreign language teaching methods in preschool education. It is envisaged that practical training will be organized orally and in writing.

During practical training, advanced pedagogical technologies are used, as well as the means of displaying demonstration slides using a computer, displaying electronic materials using a projector. In the practical training of science, it is envisaged to use innovative, interactive methods of education, as well as methods such as express questions, brainstorming, jigsaw, discussion, work in small groups, menu, debate.

In preschool education, it is required to study the subject of foreign language teaching, and in the process of independent mastering, students of the bachelor's level of education are required to acquire practical knowledge of the methodology of teaching foreign languages to children.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, the number of people of all ages learning English is increasing day by day. Because, in the process of life, living without understanding the English language is becoming more and more difficult. But language learning also depends on age.

Even, scientists have proven that children acquire language faster and easier than adults. The main reasons for this are the natural tendency of children to learn a language, their strong ability to imitate, the fact that children have enough time to learn a language compared to adults, and they keep the learned information in their memory quickly.

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